

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF In(III) IN PRESENCE OF AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF METHANOL, ETHANOL, DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE AND ACETONE

$m=3.72$ mg/sec ; $t=3.2$ sec ; $m^{1/2}t^{1/2}=2.84$ mg^{1/2}sec^{-1/2} (in 0.1M KCl, open circuit) ; $h_{corr}=72.17$ cm

Percentage of organic solvents (v/v)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (S. C. E.)	Slope (mV)	$D \times 10^6$ (cm ² /sec)	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)
0	18.80	0.53	21.4	9.48	—	—
<i>Methanol</i>						
10	16.68	0.52	44.1	7.67	1.37	9.6×10^{-7}
25	14.55	0.53	46.8	5.83	1.23	7.0×10^{-7}
50	12.06	0.55	58.8	4.00	1.15	3.0×10^{-7}
75	10.99	0.55	83.3	3.33	0.92	9.2×10^{-8}
<i>Ethanol</i>						
10	12.06	0.53	78.1	4.00	0.69	5.6×10^{-7}
15	9.58	0.54	68.2	2.53	0.63	1.2×10^{-7}
20	6.39	0.55	96.1	1.12	0.56	7.6×10^{-8}
50	4.08	0.57	97.2	0.46	0.55	2.9×10^{-8}
<i>Dimethylformamide</i>						
10	17.38	0.54	40.0	8.32	1.35	1.7×10^{-6}
25	12.59	0.55	41.6	4.37	1.30	8.4×10^{-6}
50	8.87	0.60	47.6	2.17	1.13	7.4×10^{-6}
75	6.21	0.69	58.6	1.06	0.93	3.9×10^{-6}
<i>Acetone</i>						
2	16.28	0.55	47.6	7.30	1.10	6.6×10^{-7}
4	11.09	0.56	71.4	3.39	0.76	1.5×10^{-7}
6	7.22	0.58	83.6	1.44	0.65	9.2×10^{-8}
8	6.16	0.59	89.2	1.04	0.61	6.1×10^{-8}
10	3.17	0.61	92.3	0.28	0.58	2.0×10^{-8}

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Ge(IV) IN PRESENCE OF AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF METHANOL, ETHANOL AND ACETONITRILE

$m=3.59$ mg/sec ; $t=3.2$ sec ; $m^{1/2}t^{1/2}=2.84$ mg^{1/2}sec^{-1/2} (in 0.1M NaClO₄, open circuit) ; $h_{corr}=72.17$ cm

Percentage of organic solvents (v/v)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (S. C. E.)	Slope (mV)	$D \times 10^6$ (cm ² /sec)	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)
0	22.06	1.41	130	7.54	0.40	4.0×10^{-11}
<i>Methanol</i>						
5	22.42	1.34	90	7.78	0.60	8.0×10^{-11}
10	20.93	1.35	120	6.79	0.45	9.4×10^{-11}
25	17.74	1.38	125	4.87	0.43	7.2×10^{-11}
40	16.67	1.38	127	4.30	0.42	3.9×10^{-11}
50	Wave drawn out					
<i>Ethanol</i>						
10	23.77	1.34	100	8.75	0.54	7.4×10^{-11}
25	20.22	1.37	120	6.33	0.52	6.2×10^{-11}
50	18.45	1.38	130	5.27	0.48	3.2×10^{-11}
75	17.03	1.39	135	4.49	0.42	1.6×10^{-11}
<i>Acetonitrile</i>						
10	17.38	1.41	125	4.68	0.43	4.4×10^{-11}
25	15.97	1.45	128	3.95	0.42	8.4×10^{-12}
50	14.55	1.45	130	3.28	0.41	3.1×10^{-12}
75	Wave drawn out					

follows from this that at lower percentages of these organic solvents the irreversible electrode reaction of Ge(IV) becomes less irreversible while at higher percentages it tends to become more irreversible.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. S. N. Srivastava, Principal, Agra College, Agra for necessary facilities.

References

1. I. ZLOTOWSKI and I. M. KOLTHOFF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1297.
2. G. MATSUYAMA, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Minnesota, 1948.
3. S. LAL and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Acta Chem. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1967, **53**, 127.
4. YA. ITURYAN and P. A. VYSOTSKU, *Doklady Acad. Nauk, SSSR*, 1955, **103**, 1053.
5. S. N. MUKHERJEE, A. M. GHOSH and A. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Sci. Ind. Research (India)*, 1961, **20b**, 77.
6. J. N. GAUR and D. S. JAIN, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1964, **42**, 7.
7. A. SCHWABE, "Advances in Polarography", Ed. I. S. LONGMUIR, Pergamon Press, London, 1960, vol. 3, p. 911.
8. I. TACHI and R. TAKASHI, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1960, **25**, 3111.
9. R. TAKAHASHI, *Rev. Polarogr.*, 1961, **9**, 116 ; 1963, **11**, 190.
10. J. M. HALE and R. PARSONS, "Advances in Polarography", Ed. I. S. LONGMUIR, Pergamon Press, London, 1960, vol. 3, p. 829.
11. S. LAL, S. K. JHA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 795.
12. S. LAL, P. S. JAIN and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Rev. Polarogr.*, 1969, **16**, 1.
13. S. K. JHA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1967, **40**, 810.
14. S. LAL and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **32**, 227.
15. S. K. JHA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1968, **38**, 295.
16. K. ZUTSHI, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 198.
17. T. DEVRIS and J. L. KROON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2484.
18. J. KOUTECKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, **47**, 323.
19. J. KOUTECKY, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, **18**, 597.
20. J. WEBER and J. KOUTECKY, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1955, **20**, 980.
21. J. KOUTECKY and J. OZEK, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, **21**, 836.
22. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 246.
23. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Internl. Polarogr. Congr., Prague*, 1951, **1**, 69.
24. P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4944.
25. P. KIVALO, K. B. OLDHAM and H. A. LAITINEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4148.
26. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1977, **32a**, 416.
27. P. DELAHAY, "New Instrumental Methods in Electrochemistry", Interscience Publ., New York, 1954, p. 81.
28. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 241.

Temperature Coefficient of Excess Volumes for Binary Solutions of *m*- *o*- and *p*-Xylenes in Tetrahydrofuran

S. L. OSWAL

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 26 March 1979, revised 22 April 1980, accepted 12 June 1980

IN continuation of our work¹⁻³ on thermodynamic properties of binary solutions, Oswal and Bakore⁴ recently reported the excess volumes V^E for solutions of *m*-, *o*- and *p*-xylenes in tetrahydrofuran

(THF) at 308.15 K. In this note excess volumes for the same systems at 303.15 K and 313.15 K are reported to calculate temperature coefficient $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$.

Experimental and Results

The apparatus, procedure and materials for these measurements have been described earlier⁴. A Lipkin type⁵ bicapillary pycnometer have been used for the measurement of density. The density data are correct to 0.0001.

The excess volumes V^E were calculated from the density data at 303.15 K and 313.15 K over entire range of composition from 0 to 1 for all the three systems using following relation (1).

$$V^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/d_{12} - (M_1x_1/d_1 + M_2x_2/d_2) \quad \dots (1)$$

where M, x and d represent molecular weight, mole fraction and density respectively. Subscripts 1, 2 and 12 refer to the pure components and the mixture respectively. The excess volume V^E so obtained are graphically represented in Fig. 1 for all the three systems at both the temperatures 303.15 K and 313.15 K. There is an increase in excess volume with the increase in the temperature. The excess volumes and temperature coefficient $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$ at $x_1 = x_2 = 0.5$ are listed in Table 1. The excess volumes are negative and the temperature coefficients $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$ are positive in every case.

Fig. 1. Excess volumes for three binary solutions of m-, o-, and p-xylenes in tetrahydrofuran. x_2 is the mole fraction of tetrahydrofuran.

- (a) m-xylene+THF : $\circ-\circ-\circ$ 303.15 K
 $\bullet-\bullet-\bullet$ 313.15 K
- (b) o-xylene+THF : $\triangle-\triangle-\triangle$ 303.15 K
 $\blacktriangle-\blacktriangle-\blacktriangle$ 313.15 K
- (c) p-xylene+THF : $\square-\square-\square$ 303.15 K
 $\blacksquare-\blacksquare-\blacksquare$ 313.15 K

TABLE 1—EXCESS VOLUME V^E AND TEMPERATURE COEFFICIENT $(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$ at $x_1 = x_2 = 0.5$

Systems	temp.	V^E cm ³ mole ⁻¹	$(\partial V^E/\partial T)_P$ cm ³ mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹
m-xylene+THF	303.15 K	-0.263	0.0012
	308.15 K	-0.258 ^a	
	313.15 K	-0.251	
o-xylene+THF	303.15 K	-0.285	0.0005
	308.15 K	-0.282 ^a	
	313.15 K	-0.280	
p-xylene+THF	303.15 K	-0.330	0.0048
	308.15 K	-0.310 ^a	
	303.15 K	-0.282	

a. ref. 4.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Prof. G. V. Bakore, University of Udaipur, Udaipur for necessary facilities and to C.S.I.R. New Delhi for a Post-Doctoral fellowship.

References

- D. D. DESHPANDE and S. L. OSWAL, *Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I.*, 1972, **68**, 1059.
- D. D. DESHPANDE and S. L. OSWAL, *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, 1975, **7**, 155.
- S. L. OSWAL and D. D. DESHPANDE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 798.
- S. L. OSWAL and G. V. BAKORE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17A**, 89.
- M. R. LIPKIN, J. T. DAVISON, W. T. HARVEY and S. S. KURTZ, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 55.

Salting of Naphthols

RATNA GHOSH* and BHARATI DAS

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 672, U.P.

Manuscript received 29 August 1980, revised 2 September 1981, accepted 14 September 1981

INTRODUCTION of neutral salts into the aqueous phase increases the partition coefficients of organic solutes between organic solvents and water¹. The phenomenon depends on the influence of the salts on water structure. In salt solutions which are known to be structure breakers, the trend is toward salting-out. Several theoretical approaches²⁻⁸ have been used with varying degrees of success. In salt solutions of polar nonelectrolyte solutes, the molecular interactions are more complex and the pattern of solubility behaviour is less readily predictable.

The present work is concerned with the salting-out studies on α - and β -naphthols. The naphthol activity coefficients, standard free energy, enthalpy and entropy of transfer from water to the salt solutions have been evaluated.

* To whom all correspondence should be addressed. Present address : Chemistry Department, I.I.T., Kharagpur-721 302.